

Joint Eurodoc and MCAA statement on the situation in Ukraine

The European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (Eurodoc) and the Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA) stand in solidarity with the people of Ukraine and condemn the recent acts of war from Russia. As part of the international movement of doctoral candidates and researchers at all career stages, we are particularly concerned for all students, doctoral candidates, and other researchers affiliated with academic institutions and other research facilities of Ukraine.

We would like to stress the impact of the alarming situation and the immediate as well as long-term devastating effects on the country and society.

Eurodoc and MCAA call on all European research institutions to suspend all scientific cooperation with Russia on research fields that have an immediate or potential military application.

Eurodoc and MCAA call on the governments of European countries to allow Ukrainian students, doctoral candidates and researchers to stay in Europe.

Following the devastating events in Ukraine, Eurodoc and MCAA are seriously concerned about the threat to the lives of Ukrainian researchers and to their human rights, including Academic Freedom. We call on all parties to ensure the protection of civilians, including researchers in Ukraine.

Eurodoc and MCAA call on international society to stand firm against this aggression. In particular, we call on all the European institutions to take action against Russian aggression.

We urge all our partners to stand with us and the Ukrainian people and researchers.

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